

PRI.FOR.MAN Dashboard: Overview of Wood Resources at NUT3 Level to Support Wood Mobilization and Value Chain

Introduction

Supporting wood mobilization and establishing new value chains in a forest area involves the development of a comprehensive framework and system to optimize the utilization of forest resources, enhance economic value, and promote sustainable forest management practices. The setup of a new value chain focused on wood mobilization in a forest area requires a holistic approach that considers various aspects such as forest management, stakeholder collaboration, market dynamics, and sustainability principles. Through strategic planning and implementation, a well-designed value chain can contribute to the economic growth, environmental protection, and social well-being of the forest area and its surrounding communities.

One of the initial steps in establishing a value chain and improving wood mobilization is analysing the existing wood resources and assessing their potential for value-added products and services. In this context, PRI.FOR.MAN has developed different forest geographic layers that describe forest resources, including the Growing Stock Volume map and Forest Types maps. Additionally, the OG has developed additional geographic layers, such as the Accessibility map of forest parcels and forest roads, which are important for analysing the resources for wood mobilization. All these maps have been implemented in a Decision Support System accessible through the internet.

To provide forest stakeholders at the NUT3 level with an overview of forest resources, PRI.FOR.MAN has also developed an easy-to-use dashboard that provides summarized information. This dashboard utilizes the forest geographic layers to present valuable insights and information on forest resources in a specific major area (NUT3). It features easily understandable graphs and tables that provide data on the forest area managed under forest management plans, the area accessible through two specific harvesting systems (tractor and cable yard, the most commonly used systems in the Friuli Venezia Giulia Alps), and the Growing Stock Volume accessible for the two harvesting systems. Furthermore, the dashboard provides the Growing Stock Volume accessible for each forest type, enabling an understanding of the potential wood products that can be obtained.

The dashboard serves as a tool to identify areas in the region where new value chains linked with wood mobilization can potentially be established. Moreover, the data can be easily updated when new maps of forest resources are designed. The dashboard is intended for use by public bodies and forest companies to monitor the state of forests in Friuli Venezia Giulia. The availability of such comprehensive and accessible data was not present at the regional level before the establishment of PRI.FOR.MAN OG. The dashboard developed by PRI.FOR.MAN represents a crucial first step in identifying potential wood mobilization areas, which in turn aids in the development of value chains. Additionally, the dashboard, by providing information on the Growing Stock Volume accessible through two harvesting systems, can be utilized to identify areas where the road network is not well established, thus highlighting the need for investments in road planning.

Lessons learned

Creating user-friendly dashboards that provide useful information in the form of graphs or tables for identifying areas where new value chains can be established and promoting wood mobilization is not technically challenging when the maps developed within the PRI.FOR.MAN project are available. However, it requires a significant coordination effort among public administrators and developers. Access to the necessary data for generating the forest maps, which serve as the foundation of the system, is crucial and requires coordination between different stakeholders.

Furthermore, it would be desirable for this type of activity to be carried out by the public administration, as they can play a key role in incentivizing the emergence of new value chains through policies and measures. The members of the GO strongly believe that such dashboards should be developed for public utility, providing support to the forest sector. PRI.FOR.MAN has successfully demonstrated that the development of dashboards is feasible and can be easily implemented, even within Forest Information Systems.

For further information contact

Francesca Giannetti, Assistant Professor, University of Florence, Italy, e-mail: francesca.giannetti@unifi.it
 Giorgio Alberti, University of Udine, Italy, e-mail: giorgio.alberti@unud.it
 Luca Cadez, University of Udine, Italy, e-mail: luca.cadez@uniud.it

The information presented in this factsheet was developed by the FOREST4EU partner, drawing on the innovations and knowledge generated by the indicated operational group with their explicit authorization.

Further information

https://lookerstudio.google.com/u/0/reporting/2f6c2f81-b78f-446c-ab07-96571d7b6984/page/p_w5k3gvls6c

 <small>Website</small>			
<small>Funded by the European Union (Grant n. 101086216). Views and opinions expressed are however those of the authors only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or REA. Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.</small>			